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English as Medium of Instruction (EMI) Setting: Challenges and Coping Strategies of English Major Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the different challenges and coping strategies of English major learners toward the use of English as medium of instruction (EMI) in the teaching and learning process and its significant difference when grouped according to their demographic profiles such as age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended. This utilized a descriptive design wherein descriptive was used in identifying the socio-demographic profile of the respondents and the challenges and coping strategies of the learners when grouped according to their socio-demographic profile. In collecting the quantitative data through an online survey – questionnaire with a total of 40 questions among the 78 population of BSED – English major learners at one of the colleges in Midsayap, using a Likert scale. It yielded that speaking was the most challenging, while listening was perceived as the least challenging. Learners mostly used self-motivation to cope with the challenges brought by EMI. The study's findings are a call for critical attention for English teachers to focus more on enhancing the learners' speaking skills.

Keywords: *English as medium of instruction, EMI challenges, coping strategies*

Introduction

In the 21st century, English has become an inseparable part of the educational curriculum in most countries where English is used as a second language (Akbari, 2018). However, English is perceived as one of the most challenging languages to learn and master, mainly because of its pronunciation, grammar, structure, and vocabulary complexities. Learners commonly face difficulties in speaking, listening, writing, and reading.

English as a medium of instruction (EMI) is defined as the use of the English language in teaching academic subjects other than English in countries where most of their populations' first language is not English (Macaro, 2018). English as the medium of instruction is used not only for delivering instruction and materials but it is also used entirely in the teaching-learning process. Further, learners use this in doing presentations, discussions, asking and answering questions. The development of English as EMI is of great interest to language policy researchers and has been a subject of broad research in the globalization and internationalization era. Despite the recognition of some implementation problems and constraints, EMI has been widely introduced in various non-native English-speaking countries, including Thailand (Luangangoon, 2020). Like some of the ASEAN countries, it has become a dominant medium of instruction in the country.

Although research has studied the challenges and coping strategies inside the EMI classroom, no study has identified its significant difference when the learners are grouped according to age, sex, year level, and previous senior high school attended. Especially in our country, there are limited existing studies that explore this. The abovementioned study focused solely on the challenges and coping strategies among the teachers in EMI in the Philippine setting. Locally, no study investigated English major learners' challenges and coping strategies. Hence, this study seeks to fill this gap in the EMI literature by studying the challenges and coping strategies of English major learners in the EMI setting and its significant difference in terms of age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended.

Research Questions

This study examined the challenges and coping strategies of English major learners in English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI). Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended?
2. What are the challenges faced by the learners in an EMI classroom setting in terms of speaking, listening, writing, and reading?
3. What are the coping strategies made by the learners in terms of self-motivation, compensatory strategy, social support, and task-related strategy to overcome such challenges?
4. Is there a significant difference between the challenges of the respondents when grouped according to age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended?
5. Is there a significant difference in coping strategies of the respondents when grouped according to age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended?

Literature Review

The English language is immensely growing as medium of instruction in school and university's curricula. Despite the considerable

number of schools that have already adopted it, especially in countries where English is used as a second language, there are still many groups of students who find this language difficult to learn (Phyak, 2018).

Challenges of the Learners in the EMI Setting

According to UNESCO, the lack of language proficiency and competence in language teaching, combined with the challenges students face when learning a language unfamiliar to them, caused teachers and learners in classrooms to face severe communication and learning problems. When the language of communication is foreign to the teacher or the learners, many vital issues are misunderstood or unrecognized. As a result, learners become even more unwilling to participate as they try to avoid embarrassment in front of their classmates. Furthermore, Macaro et al. (2018) pointed out several studies that reported that students' perceptions of their English proficiency align with those of their lectures and those students have difficulty understanding their lectures. In addition, Kara et al. (2019) stated that challenges may vary according to age; similarly, Mittleman (2021) concluded that challenges may differ according to sex. Pun et al. (2021) emphasized the perspective of sex differences. In terms of the challenges of the learners according to their year level, the study by Aizawa and Rose (2019) revealed that there was no indication that the challenges of the learners were heavily impacted by their years of study. Further, challenges may also be affected by the background of the previous school attended.

Speaking

Speaking in a second language, particularly English, could influence us to experience various psychological issues such as anxiety and self-confidence, as these skills have components necessary to be mastered by English learners. Thus, it is inevitable that those components may raise pressure in speaking. Speaking skills became problematic as other factors affected it, such as the learners' self-confidence and lack of vocabulary (Nadila et al., 2020). Additionally, the study shows that aside from self-confidence itself, there are also a lot of factors that affect it, such as being embarrassed and scared of their classmates' reaction if they will speak incorrectly in the English language, having lack of knowledge in vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation.

Listening

Listening is an everyday activity with a massive role in receiving information (Nushi & Orouji, 2020). Listeners are vital in understanding its process by applying their knowledge to what they hear to understand what the speaker means, especially when listeners are in a school. Meanwhile, EMI teachers described learners as "weak in following fast speakers" and "passive learners." Likewise, many factors may affect the learners' listening comprehension (Sahlen et al., 2020). Moreover, according to Yilmaz and Yavuz (2018), there are many difficulties in listening comprehension. Many learners struggle with listening comprehension assessments because they no longer remember the information they may have listened to. Additionally, cited in the study by Assaf (2018), it has revealed that learners encountered difficulties such as not understanding the topic while listening to text, noise, and speech rate.

Writing

Academic writing is considered the most challenging for university students (Jiang et al., 2022). The result of their study reported that among their participants, 12 interviewees revealed that they were experiencing language difficulties. Most of them mentioned that their poor grammar and lack of vocabulary in English significantly impacted their writing process. While in the setting of Pakistan, students are facing severe writing difficulties. One of the major writing issues that the learners are experiencing is the organization of ideas (Siddiqui, 2020). He discussed that the reason behind the deficiency of the learners is the teacher factor. They are lacking of training and skills to impart to the learners. Due to this serious matter, learners are used to copying and reproducing paragraphs whenever they are in a writing activity.

Reading

Reading skills are considered one of the essential skills one must master efficiently before succeeding in the academic field (Çiftlikli, 2018). Oxford Dictionary defines reading as the particular way in which someone understands a book, situation, etc. Among the students majoring in English, reading is one of the main problems of learners, along with speaking (Xiao & Zou, 2020). Learners have difficulty understanding English academic text, figuring out its structure, and understanding vocabulary. Identifying the main or key ideas, pronunciation of unfamiliar words, and their nervousness during reading activity is also reported by the learners as their challenges. Anwar and Sailuddin (2022) found that academic reading is considered an easy task among learners. Despite this result, they are still facing some difficulties, as rated by the respondents.

Coping Strategy of the Learners in the EMI Setting

According to the APA (American Psychological Association), a coping mechanism is any conscious or no conscious adjustment or adaptation that decreases tension and anxiety in a stressful experience or situation. Challenges will always be associated with coping mechanisms. As a result, the students discovered a way to cope with the challenges given by the EMI setting. This study recognized the positive impact and the importance of using the mother tongue in an EMI setting (Ali, 2020).

According to Alrashidi (2021), learning strategies do not rely on their year of study. His study explored the learning strategy of the English major learners in Saudi Arabia. He discussed that learners' majoring in English are aware of the importance of these strategies,

regardless of their age.

Self-motivation

Self-motivation is one of the coping strategies that can be applied to reduce the challenges in an EMI classroom setting. Seven (2020) defined self-motivation as staying motivated by one's interest. It is vital in one's life as it allows self-assessment as often as possible. In pursuit of being highly motivated, a person must know the results, have high aspirations, and have a clear goal is very important, especially if the student is encouraged to set his own goals and seek superior remote goals. Seven (2020) also mentioned several steps to be self-motivated, especially in language learning: (1) Write down your goals and focus on those goals; (2) Motivate yourself to reach those goals; (3) Identify and measure specific behaviors needed to reach your goals; (4) Arrange your environment to facilitate study, (5) Monitor your self-messages, when you hear a negative self-statement, try telling yourself to stop, (7) Avoid extreme anxiety, as it is irrational. With these, even though anxiety cannot be avoided, it can be reduced.

Compensatory Strategy

The compensatory strategy is defined as language-solving techniques that consist of various mental or physical activities carried out by the learners to resolve any language problem they encounter (Shakarami, 2018). This strategy also refers to learners finding synonyms from the context of the reading and relying mainly on non-verbal resources or communication to express the meaning when the exact meaning of the statement is not fully understood. It is divided into guessing intelligently and overcoming limitations in speaking and writing. Guessing meaning strategy helps learners intelligently guess the meaning of the phrase by using surrounding words as linguistic and non-linguistic cues.

In the study conducted by Ali (2020), the learners use numerous compensatory strategies when dealing with EMI, including using the mother tongue, translation, dictionaries and the internet, and peer, group, and family support. However, in the study conducted by Ali (2020), Arabic learners use their mother tongue as their compensatory strategy instead of relying on non-verbal resources and guessing meanings, as it is easier for them to explain and answer questions when they speak in their mother tongue and due to this they tend to code-switch.

Social support

According to the study conducted by Chien and Valcke (2020), many learners engage in group discussions using English even if they are not fluent in the language. Further, the help of classmates, friends, professionals/teachers, and family members is great to help learners who lack English vocabulary as they can understand the concepts and terms that are unfamiliar to them (Ali, 2020). However, most learners seek help from their teachers and classmates, which they consider a great help in coping with the challenges brought by EMI. In the study conducted by Xiao and Zou (2020), classmates are a great help in helping them overcome the challenges in an EMI in terms of speaking, reading, and writing. In addition, social support is highly connected to creating an environment conducive to learning. Ali et al. (2020) revealed that a conducive learning environment supports and holds the learners' interest in the long run. It also revealed that social strategies are the most accessible among learners, such as practicing speaking English with classmates.

Task-Related Strategy

Task-related strategies provide the learners with a specific task related to the real-life context. It is either in oral or written related tasks such as: Writing letters, group activities, Field trips, or anything connected to reasoning, planning, reporting, etc. Learners have been using translations from the internet or dictionaries to help them with tasks such as written assignments and projects (Ali, 2020). Some learners stated that this strategy helped them understand complex concepts in English and helped translate their mother tongue to English. However, they added also that sometimes it confuses them because when they use Google Translations, it doesn't provide the exact meaning of the word or phrase. In the study of Xiao and Zou (2020), they found that some learners record their presentations to know their weak points, regardless of how it still provides more useful functions to help students in their tasks.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researchers utilized a descriptive research design and were used to describe the distribution of one or more variables without regard to any causal or other hypotheses (Aggarwal & Ranganathan, 2018). It was descriptive since it represented the demographic profiles of the respondents (Sousa et al., 2007) and the significant difference in the respondents' challenges and coping strategies when grouped according to their age, sex, year level, and Senior High School education.

Respondents

This study was conducted at a higher education institution at Poblacion 5, Quezon Avenue, Midsayap, North Cotabato. The respondents were English majors from first to fourth-year students of the College of Education.

The sample used in this study consisted of 78 college learners from one of the colleges in Midsayap. A purposive-complete enumeration sampling technique was employed, and its main objective is to emphasize and focus on the characteristics of the chosen respondents.

Thus, this technique was utilized to purposely select all the major English learners of the institution to fill the gap found in the literature. The researchers acquired the list of the names of the respondents from the College of Education Department (CED) office.

Instruments

The questionnaire comprised three parts to obtain the necessary data for this study. The first part examined the socio-demographics of the learners, such as name (optional), age, sex, year level, and their school in Senior High School. In the second part, to determine the respondents' challenges in the EMI setting, this study used the questionnaire developed and validated by Ali (2017) based on the FLCAS by Horwitz et al. (1986). The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) developed by (Horwitz et al., 1986) has been extensively used in studies over the past 27 years and has facilitated a tremendous development in the research about EMI (Ali, 2017). The questionnaire was modified according to existing literature to contextualize the school setup and used a Likert scale. The third part contains the research-made questionnaire on the learners' coping strategies, consisting of 20 items. It was also anchored on the existing literature to contextualize the school setup. It was divided into four coping strategies such as self-motivation, compensatory strategy, social support, and task-related.

Data Analysis

The study utilized both descriptive and inferential statistics. At the descriptive level, the data's frequency distribution, mean, and percentages were used to treat the data on the demographic profile consisting of the age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School the respondents attended. Further, the statistical tool used on the challenges and coping strategies were weighted mean and standard deviation. For the inferential tool, t-Test was used to calculate the significant difference between the learners' challenges and coping strategies in an EMI setting when grouped according to age, sex, and previous school attended. Likewise, ANOVA was used to compute the significant difference between the learners' challenges and coping strategies in an EMI setting when grouped according to year level.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the result of the study in a tabular form. It covered the demographic profile of the respondents; their challenges in terms of speaking, listening, writing, and reading; coping strategies in terms of self-motivation, compensatory strategy, social support, and task-related strategy and their significant difference when they are grouped according to age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of seventy - eight respondents according to age, sex, year level, and previous Senior High School attended.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

<i>Profile of the Respondents</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Age		
11 to 20	36	46.15
21 to 30	42	53.85
Total	78	100.00
Sex		
Male	25	32.05
Female	53	67.95
Total	78	100.00
Year Level		
1st	14	17.95
2nd	23	29.49
3rd	21	26.92
4th	20	25.64
Total	78	100.00
Previous Senior High School attended		
Public	22	28.21
Private	56	71.79
Total	78	100.00

It can be seen in Table 1 that a frequency of 42 constitutes 53.85 percent were respondents aged between 21 to 30 and obtained a frequency of 36 with 46.15 percent aged between 11 to 20, respectively. Similarly, out of the 78 respondents, the frequency of 53 comprises 67.95 percent were female respondents, and a frequency of 25 with 32.05 percent were male respondents. Moreover, the frequency distribution of 23 comprises 29.49 percent were 2nd-year respondents; a frequency of 21 with 26.92 percent were 3rd-year respondents; a frequency of 20 obtained 25.64 percent were 4th-year respondents while a frequency distribution of 14 comprises 17.95 percent were 1st-year respondents. Likewise, the frequency of 56 comprises 71.79 percent were respondents who previously attended

their Senior High in a private school. In contrast, a frequency distribution of 22 constitutes 28.21 percent were from public Senior High Schools.

Challenges Faced by the Learners in Terms of Speaking, Listening, Reading, and Writing

Table 2 presents the challenges faced by the learners in terms speaking, listening, writing, and reading with the mean, standard deviation. It also contains the description and its interpretation.

Table 2. *The Challenges Faced by the Learners in Terms of Speaking, Listening, Writing, and Reading*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Speaking				
1. I worry when asked to speak in English during class discussions because of my shyness.	2.99	1.13	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
2. I am bothered when asked to deliver a presentation in English due to my limited vocabulary.	2.90	1.08	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
3. I get confused on my pronunciation when I speak English.	2.97	1.04	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
4. I lack self-confidence when I speak in English to others.	3.05	1.17	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
5. I fear being laughed by classmates whenever I speak English.	3.06	1.32	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
Overall	2.99	1.15	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
Listening				
I find difficulty in comprehending fast speakers of English.	2.86	1.04	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
I find challenging to understand lectures, news, speeches and dialogues delivered in English.	2.56	0.93	Disagree	Slightly Challenging
I find difficulty in distinguishing information that I listen through English.	2.60	0.94	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
I am having difficulty in lecture comprehension because of my poor English vocabulary	2.46	1.05	Disagree	Slightly Challenging
I am struggling to understand English class discussion due to the teacher's accent.	2.29	1.08	Disagree	Slightly Challenging
Overall	2.56	1.02	Disagree	Slightly Challenging
Writing				
I find it difficult to write because of my grammar.	2.73	1.04	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
I worry when I am asked to write because of my limited English vocabulary.	2.65	1.03	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
I have difficulty paraphrasing the thoughts of a certain English academic writing.	2.79	1.04	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
I find it hard putting my thoughts into English words.	2.69	1.06	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
It takes a long time to organize my ideas during English writing activity.	2.92	1.10	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
Overall	2.76	1.05	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
Reading				
I feel nervous when reading English that causes me to stutter.	2.33	1.02	Disagree	Slightly Challenging
I had to read the English text multiple times before I can identify the key ideas.	2.64	0.94	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
I find it challenging to understand the organization of the English text.	2.47	0.95	Disagree	Slightly Challenging
I feel doubtful with my pronunciation when I am asked to read an unfamiliar English word.	2.88	1.08	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
My limited English vocabulary affects my reading comprehension.	2.72	1.10	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
Overall	2.61	1.03	Neutral	Moderately Challenging
Grand SD and Mean	2.73	1.08	Neutral	Moderately Challenging

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Strongly Agree/Extremely Challenging, 3.50 – 4.49 Agree/Very Challenging, 2.50 – 3.49 Neutral/Moderately Challenging, 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree/Slightly Challenging, 1.00 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree/Not at all Challenging

In terms of the speaking challenges faced by the learners in an EMI setting, out of five identified challenges, all five were rated as Neutral with an overall mean of 2.99, interpreted as Moderately Challenging, and a standard deviation of 1.15. The statements that obtained the first two highest means were I fear being laughed at by classmates whenever I speak English with a 3.06 mean, and I lack self-confidence when I speak in English to others, with a 3.05 mean. Both were rated as Neutral and interpreted as Moderately Challenging. In the listening challenges, three of the five challenges were described as Neutral, and two as Disagree. It obtained an overall mean of 2.56, described as Disagree, interpreted as Slightly Challenging, and a standard deviation of 1.02. Among these challenges, results revealed that I find difficulty comprehending fast English speakers ranked the highest with a mean of 2.86. It was followed by the statement I find difficulty in distinguishing information that I listen to through English, as the second highest with a mean of 2.60. Both were described as Neutral and interpreted as Moderately Challenging.

In the writing challenges, out of five challenges, all five were described as Neutral, with an overall mean of 2.76 being described as Neutral and interpreted as Moderately Challenging and a standard deviation of 1.05. Challenges under the statement It takes a long time to organize my ideas during English writing activity obtained the highest with a mean of 2.92. At the same time, I have difficulty paraphrasing thoughts of a certain English academic writing, garnered the second highest mean of 2.79. The two were described as Neutral and interpreted as Moderately Challenging, respectively. In reading challenges, three of the five reading challenges were rated as Neutral, and two were described as Disagree, with an overall mean of 2.61 being described as Neutral and interpreted as Moderately

Challenging and a standard deviation of 1.03. Difficulties related to reading, such as I feel doubtful with my pronunciation when asked to read an unfamiliar English word and my limited English vocabulary affects my reading comprehension, have obtained the first and second highest with a mean of 2.88 and 2.72, respectively. These were all described as Neutral with an interpretation of Moderately Challenging.

Coping Strategies of the Learners in Terms of Self-motivation, Compensatory Strategy, Social Support, and Task-Related Strategy

Table 3 shows the coping strategies of the learners in an EMI setting with mean and standard deviation.

Table 3. *The Coping Strategies of the Learners in Terms of Self-motivation, Compensatory Strategy, Social Support, and Task-Related Strategy*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Self-motivation				
1. I write my goals every week (e.g., learn new vocabularies through reading English book).	3.37	1.03	Neutral	Sometimes
2. I set and identify set of behaviors in order to achieve my goals.	3.55	1.01	Agree	Often
3. I find positive environment to study.	4.08	0.86	Agree	Often
4. I set aside negative thoughts.	3.96	0.97	Agree	Often
5. I motivate myself to improve through speaking English when I am alone.	4.18	0.85	Agree	Often
Overall	3.83	1.00	Agree	Often
Compensatory Strategy				
1. I use my mother tongue or L1 to deliver ideas which I can't express in English.	3.47	0.95	Neutral	Sometimes
2. I am code-switching to express my ideas better (for example, from English to Filipino).	3.73	0.88	Agree	Often
3. I am using linguistic clues such as my knowledge in suffixes, prefixes and word in order to guess the meaning of an unfamiliar word.	3.78	0.86	Agree	Often
4. I am using non-linguistic clues in order to guess the meaning of what is heard or read in the target language (ex. knowledge of context).	3.63	0.85	Agree	Often
5. I am using non-verbal cues to successfully express my ideas.	3.64	0.90	Agree	Often
Overall	3.65	0.89	Agree	Often
Social Support				
1. I ask my classmate for the unfamiliar words or phrases in English that I can't understand.	3.85	0.87	Agree	Often
2. I ask an educated family member for the unfamiliar words or phrases in English that confuses me.	3.58	1.03	Agree	Often
3. I practice English with my friends.	3.74	0.93	Agree	Often
4. Our teacher let us practice English by using it throughout the whole class duration.	4.10	0.80	Agree	Often
5. I and my classmates have group discussions to critique each other.	3.31	1.12	Neutral	Sometimes
Overall	3.72	0.99	Agree	Often
Task-Related Strategy				
1. I use mind-mapping when given a reading task.	3.64	0.72	Agree	Often
2. I read translations (Filipino-English) in the internet.	3.69	1.01	Agree	Often
3. I memorize the things I will say before my presentation.	3.62	0.94	Agree	Often
4. I summarize the thoughts of every paragraph to have a better understanding of what I am reading.	4.01	0.81	Agree	Often
5. I ask a classmate to record my presentation, so I can review my performance and know about my weak points.	3.19	1.17	Neutral	Sometimes
Overall	3.63	0.98	Agree	Often
Grand SD and Mean	3.71	0.97	Agree	Often

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Strongly Agree/Always, 3.50 – 4.49 Agree/Often, 2.50 – 3.49 Neutral/Sometimes, 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree/Seldom, 1.00 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree/Never

Out of the five identified coping strategies under self-motivation, one was rated as Neutral, and four as Agree, with an overall mean of 3.83, described as Agree and interpreted as Often, and a standard deviation of 1.00. The statement, I motivate myself to improve through speaking English when I am alone got the highest mean of 4.18 which was described as Agree and interpreted as Often. While the second highest mean is the statement, I find a positive environment to study, obtained a 4.08 mean which was described as Agree and interpreted as Often. In the compensatory strategy, out of the identified coping strategies, one was rated as Neutral, and four as Agree, with a garnered mean of 3.65, described as Agree and interpreted as Often, and a standard deviation of 0.89. The statement, I am using linguistic clues such as my knowledge in suffixes, prefixes, and words to guess the meaning of an unfamiliar word, obtained the highest mean of 3.78, described as Agree and interpreted as Often. While the statement, I am code-switching to express my ideas better (for example, from English to Filipino garnered the second highest mean of 3.73, which was also described as Agree and interpreted as Often.

In the social support, out of the identified coping strategies, one was rated as Neutral, and four as Agree with an obtained 3.72 mean which was described as Agree and interpreted as Often with an overall standard deviation of 0.99. Out of the five statements, the

statement Our teacher let us practice English by using it throughout the whole class duration, garnered the highest mean of 4.10, which was described as Agree and interpreted as Often. While the statement, I ask my classmate for the unfamiliar words or phrases in English that I can't understand, got the second highest mean of 3.85, described as Agree and interpreted as Often. Under the task-related strategy, out of the identified coping strategies, one was also rated as Neutral, and four as Agree with an obtained mean of 3.63, which was described as Agree and interpreted as Often and an overall standard deviation of 0.98. The statement, I summarize the thoughts of every paragraph to understand better what I am reading, obtained the highest mean of 4.01, described as Agree and interpreted as Often. While I read translations (Filipino-English) online, the statement garnered the second highest mean of 3.69, described as Agree and interpreted as Often.

Differences in the Challenges of the Respondents When Grouped According to Age, Sex, Year Level, and Previous Senior High School Attended

Table 4 shows the used of t-Test and ANOVA. The t-Test was the appropriate statistical tool in determining the significant differences between the challenges of the learners when grouped according to their age, sex and previous senior high attended. While ANOVA (Analysis of Variance), a statistical formula that is used in analyzing the differences across the average or means of more than three independent groups was utilized in determining the significant differences of the learner's challenges when grouped according to their year level.

Table 4. *Differences on the Challenges of the Respondents When Grouped According to Age, Sex, Year Level, and Previous Senior High School Attended*

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	p-value	Indication	Decision
Age							
11-20	36	3.01	0.63	76	0.003	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
21-30	42	2.49	0.83				
Sex							
Female	53	2.82	0.76	77	0.20	Not Significant	Do Not Reject the Null Hypothesis
Male	25	2.47	0.78				
Year Level							
1 st year	14	2.98	0.75	77	0.15	Not Significant	Do Not Reject the Null Hypothesis
2 nd year	23	2.90	0.78				
3 rd year	21	2.65	0.72				
4 th year	20	2.45	0.82				
Previous Senior High School Attended							
Private	56	2.81	0.76	76	0.14	Not Significant	Do Not Reject the Null Hypothesis
Public	22	2.52	0.82				

Table 4 contains the results of the test on the significant differences on the challenges of learners when grouped according to age, sex, year level, and previous senior high school attended.

The t-test result on the significant differences in the challenges of the learners, when grouped according to age, acquired a p-value of 0.003, which indicated that it was significant at a 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. In addition, the t-test result on the significant differences in the challenges of the learners, when grouped according to sex, acquired a p-value of 0.20, indicating that it was not significant at a 0.05 significance level; thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

The result of the ANOVA test on the significant differences in the challenges of the learners, when grouped according to year level, acquired a p-value of 0.15, which indicated that it was not significant at a 0.05 significance level; thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected. Meanwhile, the result of the t-test on the significant differences in the challenges of the learners, when grouped according to previous senior high school attended, acquired a p-value of 0.14, which indicated that it was not significant at 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Differences in the Coping Strategies of the Respondents When Grouped According to Age, Sex, Year Level, and Previous Senior High School Attended

Table 5 shows the used of t-Test and ANOVA. The t-Test was the appropriate statistical tool in determining the significant differences between the coping strategies of the learners when grouped according to their age, sex and previous senior high attended. While ANOVA (Analysis of Variance), a statistical formula that is used in analyzing the differences across the average or means of more than three independent groups was utilized in determining the significant differences of the learner's coping strategies when grouped according to their year level.

Table 5 contains the results of the test on the significant differences on the coping strategies of learners when grouped according to age, sex, year level, and previous senior high school attended.

The result of the t-test on the significant differences in the coping strategies of the learners, when grouped according to age, acquired a p-value of 0.35, which indicates it was not significant at 0.05 level of significance; hence, it does not reject the null hypothesis.

Meanwhile, the t-test result on the significant differences in the coping strategies of the learners, when grouped according to sex, acquired a p-value of 0.60, which is not significant at 0.05 level of significance, and does not reject the null hypothesis.

Table 5. *Differences on the Coping Strategies of the Respondents When Grouped According to Age, Sex, Year Level, and Previous Senior High School Attended*

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	p-value	Indication	Decision
Age							
11-20	36	3.64	0.45	76	0.35	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
21-30	42	3.76	0.62				
Sex							
Female	53	3.69	0.55	77	0.60	Not Significant	Do Not Reject the Null Hypothesis
Male	25	3.70	0.50				
Year Level							
1 st year	14	3.56	0.35	77	0.29	Not Significant	Do Not Reject the Null Hypothesis
2 nd year	23	3.65	0.53				
3 rd year	21	3.69	0.62				
4 th year	20	3.90	0.58				
Previous Senior High School Attended							
Private	56	3.67	0.60	76	0.35	Not Significant	Do Not Reject the Null Hypothesis
Public	22	3.80	0.39				

Further, a result of the ANOVA test on the significant differences in the coping strategies of the learners, when grouped according to year level, acquired a p-value of 0.29, which is not significant at a 0.05 significance level; thus, it does not reject the null hypothesis. Also, the t-test result on the significant differences in the coping strategies of the learners, when grouped according to previous senior high school attended, acquired a p-value of 0.35, which is not significant at a 0.05 level of significance and does not reject the null hypothesis.

Conclusion

After extensive data collection and analysis, this study concluded that the English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) setting is moderately challenging among major English learners. Most of the respondents in this study identify that their speaking skill through English as a medium of Instruction is a very crucial skill they need to master, given the fact that they struggled with it the most. On the other hand, when they are dealing with the challenges brought by EMI, they are only often using self-motivation to ease their difficulties. Learners thrive on motivating themselves alone by practicing speaking in English. In addition, there was no significant difference on the learners' challenges towards EMI classroom setting when grouped according to their socio-demographic characteristics such as year level, gender and previous senior high school attended except for their ages. Meanwhile, there was also no significant difference on the learners' coping strategies when grouped according to their socio-demographic characteristics such as age, gender, year level and previous senior school attended.

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